

Evaluating the Impact of Library Service Quality on Library Usage by Undergraduate Students in Nigeria Private Universities

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Abstract

Keywords:

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Introduction

The study examined how accessible, comprehensive, and well-managed library services contribute to students' library usage.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. A proportionate random sampling technique was used to select four private universities in Ogun State. Krejcie and Morgan's table was used to select 370 students from the four universities. An adapted and validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Out of 370 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 255 were returned, making a 68.9% response rate. Data was analyzed using SPSS software. Percentage, mean, and inferential statistics were used to interpret the results.

Findings/Results

Results indicate that the level of service quality is moderately high, and library usage revealed a moderately high extent (grand mean = 3.0). The hypothesis revealed a significant influence of library service quality on library usage.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is a positive significant influence of the quality of service on library usage.

Recommendations

The study recommended training and retraining of the library staff to ensure the quality of services rendered to the students. Additionally, library management should develop constant user perspective evaluation strategies encompassing all aspects of library services.

Introduction

Libraries have always been crucial because they provide access to a wide range of knowledge and information resources. Service quality refers to the degree to which a service meets or exceeds customer expectations. It is a measure of how well a service is delivered and how it satisfies customers' needs and desires. Service quality in general is a concept which can translate into customers' satisfaction for example; a customer made a purchase at XYZ departmental store and headed to his car, out of the three packages he had purchased, he forgot one at the store and left. The customer returned in a short while to claim the package, but it was gone. He checked with security to see if someone had found the package, but no one had. As a gesture of goodwill, the store keeper replaced the products the customer had lost without collecting any money from him again. Can you imagine how pleasantly surprised the customer must have been? He must be extremely delighted with the service experience that he received at the store.

From the example given above, you may conclude that service quality relates to providing a total experience rather than only basic services. Knowing fully well that service is characterised as intangible and perishable. However, the effects of experiences generated by high quality service encounters are recollected by customers for a long time. This is not only helps in retaining customers by increasing their loyalty, but also creates a positive word of mouth that can bring in more customers.

Quality of service in any business organization or service oriented organisation should be an important variable to measure usage and satisfaction of customers. Service quality is defined as "the difference between the actual customer expectations of services and the perceived services" (Kiriri, 2018). If the

services offered by libraries, especially university libraries are of good quality, there is surely no doubt, that the library users will place value on them. The users of academic libraries include faculty members, researchers, teaching and non-teaching staffs, students and community members. Academic libraries strive to serve its users or clients with high-quality services (Barfi et al., 2023). The quality of library services offered to clients or users may have a favorable impact on their information needs and seeking behavior. The need for service providers to consistently measure the performance of educational facilities' service quality is highly necessary particularly quality library services for continuous improvement in satisfying students' access to library resources. This is because students are directly involved in the usage of library resources in advancing their education process, hence it is essential to sample their views on the quality of services rendered in the library as well as the usage of the library.

The outcome of such research is expected to help the service provider to make judgment about the level of the quality of facilities provided in the higher institutions like universities. One of such facilities in institutions that students' opinion should be sought for maintaining academic excellence is the library. An effective and efficient academic library system is expected to contribute significantly to students' development in terms of quality resources such as books, journals, e-resources and online databases which will invariably enhance patronage of students to the library. A library is effective when it is able to meet its users' needs relative to its mission and objectives. The main component of every institution is the library and hence, if the resources are there and it is under utilised by the students, it will undermine the good purposes of the library and thereby discourage in equipping the library with resources.

Libraries give users access to a plethora of information sources and interactive communication opportunities. Academic libraries' traditional duty is to make current, high-quality, and pertinent information resources available to support teaching, learning, and research in the middle of other duties. The supply of pertinent information sources and services for library users is typically viewed as the reason for the existence of the library, and if its users do not utilize the resources and services it provides, the purpose of a library is thwarted. Libraries play a crucial role in providing access to various information sources and communication opportunities for users. Academic libraries, in particular, focus on offering current, high-quality resources to support teaching, learning, and research. The essence of a library lies in its ability to provide relevant resources and services for its users. This user-centric approach is guided by laws, principles, and guidelines that prioritize the satisfaction of library users. The "five laws of library users" underscore the importance of information satisfaction as the primary purpose of a library's existence. While initially centered on books as the main information resource, the evolving landscape of knowledge has expanded the library's role to include various information formats.

These laws emphasize the user's right to access and utilize information resources efficiently, highlighting the need for libraries to adapt to technological advancements and changing user expectations. Two key implications emerge from these laws. Firstly, library personnel must prioritize saving the user's time by delivering quality and timely services both onsite and online. Secondly, libraries must evolve to remain relevant in the digital age, transitioning from traditional book-centric services to embracing e-books, online resources, and other technological innovations. Ultimately, improving service quality is essential for enhancing student satisfaction

with library services. In higher educational settings such as universities, several instruments for measuring service quality have been developed and formalised by authors such as SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 1985, 1988; Zeithaml et al., 1990).

The SERVQUAL model, based on the idea of user-centred assessment, identified five potential gaps between expectations and perceptions, both internal and external, of service delivery. The gaps summarised by Nitecki (1996) are the discrepancy between customers' expectations and managements' perceptions of these expectations; discrepancy between managements' perceptions of customers' expectations and service quality specifications; discrepancy between service quality specifications and actual service delivery; discrepancy between actual service delivery and what is communicated to customers about it; and discrepancy between customers' expected services and perceived service delivered. Gap five is the most user-focused, customer-oriented definition of service quality, and the conceptual basis for the SERVQUAL instrument (Nitecki, 1996). According to Fedoroff (2006) the SERVQUAL model was originally based around five key dimensions of service: Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy.

Fedoroff (2006) and Nagata et al (2004) pointed out that these dimensions had been adopted later to cover the following: Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Competence; possession of required skill and knowledge to perform service, Courtesy, politeness, respect, consideration and friendliness of contact personnel, Credibility; trustworthiness, believability, honesty of the service provider, Security; freedom from danger, risk, or doubt, Access – employees who are approachable and easy to contact, Communication; listening to customers and acknowledging their comments; keeping

customers informed; and using a language they can understand, and Understanding the customer; making the effort to know customers and their needs.

Service quality focuses specifically on dimensions of service. Parasuraman et al (1998) defined Reliability as the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. Assessing the quality of library services involves evaluating various dimensions: Responsiveness; the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. Assurance is the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Empathy involves the caring, individualized attention given to customers. Tangibles entail the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials.

High quality library services rely on various factors such as the physical environment and digital resources available to users that would make them patronize the library. The major determinant for the library usage by the students is the access to electronic resources which might give vast quantities of information, a variety of search possibilities, simple citations, ease of uploading and updating which can be simultaneously accessed by multiple users.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The academic library stands as a vital resource hub for educational information, pivotal in aiding study and research endeavors. Recent advancements in technology have led to the modernization of library services, notably the development of extensive online databases brimming with educational materials. Despite these strides, educational institutions often fail to harness the full potential of library services, hindering the realization of educational benefits associated with library use (Jamilah, 2020).

Previous research indicates a concerning trend of underutilization among library users, particularly undergraduates, despite the institution's goal to expand information access (Ntemana & Olatokun, 2012; Fagan, 2014). However, limited studies have explored the quality of library services in university settings, particularly within academic libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Against this backdrop, this study endeavors to examine the impact of library service quality on the utilization of libraries by undergraduates. Through this investigation, the aim is to shed light on the factors influencing library usage patterns and identify areas for improvement in service delivery to enhance the overall educational experience for students.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the level of service quality provided by libraries to undergraduates of private universities in Ogun state, Nigeria.
2. To find out the extent of library usage by undergraduates of private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of service quality provided by libraries to undergraduates of private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of library usage by undergraduate of private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of library service quality on library usage by undergraduate students of private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Library Service Quality (LIBSERVQUAL) SERVQUAL was first developed by Parasuraman et al (1988). It is an assessment tool for service quality of organizations. Quality means the degree of goodness as per the specifications and standard. Quality is the standard of something as measured against other things of a similar kind or the degree of excellence of something. Library service is considered of good quality, when it fulfills the need of the users.

Although the concept of service quality is not new but measuring service quality as a management technique has gained much importance over the last few decades in most service organization (Partap, 2019). Measuring quality services is therefore a comprehensive and structured approach to organizational management that seeks to improve the quality of products and services through ongoing refinements in response to continuous feedback.

Service quality entails how well services align with user expectations. Employing the SERVQUAL model, the research evaluates library resources, facilities and staff interactions' impact on user satisfaction (Emiri and Olise, 2023). Majority of research work in and outside Nigeria on the quality of library services have adopted the SERVQUAL instrument.

Library information resources are information carriers with various media, including books, serials, maps, CDs, and more. Library information resources, in the words of another scholar are possible information carriers found in the library collection (Rasheed, 2014). Some scholars agreed that, libraries are in the business of giving their user community access to informational items and services. This indicates that any library material used to

inform library patrons falls under the category of library information resources.

Research on the lack of books in Nigeria and the threat to academic excellence conducted by a scholar proved that a lack of information resources has discouraged faculty members and students from using the services of libraries (Mahwasane, 2016). The extent to which library service quality are assessed depends on the availability of information resources rendered and the utilization of facilities by library users.

The currency and relevancy of the information resources properly arrange on shelves, the usefulness of its catalogs and finding tools in providing access to its collection, the ability and cooperation of library staff to use the facilities to bring these information resources and services to the attention of the users, the attitude of the staff in rendering services are some of the requirements necessary for measuring service quality. Library service quality focuses on how well services are delivered, compared to user's expectations. Library service quality assesses whether services rendered conforms to the expectations of users.

Libraries that meet or exceed expectations are considered to have high library services. The fact remains that any library is in the business of offering services to its users. For library to be functional, the services it provides should correspond with the needs of its users because the user is the very reason for the existence of the library and it ensures that the service provided are exploited to the maximum.

Any library that want to improve its services to meet the views, opinions and perceptions of users must solicit the help of users to identify its areas of weaknesses in order to improve upon them. Nyantakyi (2016) stated that if the service provided in university libraries meets users' information needs or expectations, it

can be considered that there is quality service when the information meets users' need and their expectation.

It is fundamental to note that the degree to which the library services are perceived as having a well quality and valuable resources depends totally on the availability of relevant and current electronic and print resources, modern activities or services, and facilities which in turn, affects users' attitude towards the use of library services. Kiriri (2018, p. 22), noted that the success of a library in achieving its target in terms of vision and mission is closely linked to how its users perceive the services offered as well as their attitude towards the use of library services.

Library Usage of Undergraduates

Various users of libraries around the world have expressed their satisfactory level with the usage of library based on either the attitude of library personnel, quality services or resources available. For instance, most students complain about the university library hall's lack of group study rooms, quiet spaces, and full-text publications during busy times. Some other library users worldwide have expressed user dissatisfaction in library usage (Yelinek et al., 2005; Fagan, 2014; Messengale et al., 2016; Imamoglu & Gurel 2016).

A study by Maina et al. (2017) on "Usage and User Satisfaction of Library Resources in Kisii University Library, Kenya" stated that, most respondents were reported as being satisfied by the available resources. However, information communication technologies were cited as the way to go in order to meet user needs. As such, academic libraries must invest more on e-resources and library management systems. Maina et al. (2017) also showed that library resources were not introduced or advertised to them by library personnel as many users were reported to have known the existence of a given material in the library

from a colleague or friend, leaving librarians with a small percentage served. Fagyan et al. (2023) identified the reasons for the variance in the usage of library. They include; poor knowledge of students about library resources, lack of resources which may prohibit the library from satisfying student needs, bad library service and inconvenient hours of operation. Further, despite the benefits derived from the library, many students are dissatisfied with local libraries' amenities and services. According to Sahu & Dash (2021), students were unhappy with library staff, resource availability and convenience.

Theoretical Review

LibQUAL Model

Libqual is a web-based survey offered by the Association of Research Libraries that helps libraries assess and improve library services, change organizational culture, and market the library. The program's centerpiece is a rigorously tested Web-based survey bundled with training that helps libraries assess and improve library services, change organizational culture, and market the library (Yaya, 2019).

Library administrators have successfully used libqual survey data to identify best practices, analyze deficits, and effectively allocate resources. Libqual gives librarians a chance to tell where their services need improvement so they can respond to and better manage users expectations. Affect of Service essentially condenses three of the Servqual-identified service dimensions—Assurance, Empathy, and Responsiveness—into one. Through qualitative analysis, it was discovered that reliability, or the capacity to deliver promised or expected services dependably and accurately, was just as crucial in the library setting as it was in earlier servqual-assessed sectors (Otieno et al., 2015).The idea that a library is a place reflects a concept that goes beyond servqual Tangibles. The ability to

provide a practical area for study, cooperation, or rendezvous is evaluated by the "Library as Place" concept. This is frequently crucial for undergraduates because their options are more constrained than those of graduate and faculty students. Interviews with participants suggested that some people regarded the availability of attractive library space as a symbol of the importance of the intellectual life in higher education (Popoola and Zaid, 2007). It connotes making electronic resources accessible from users home or office; a library Web site that enables users to locate information on their own, the printed library materials they need on their own should be easily navigable through the electronic information resources of a library.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design to investigate the relationship between library service quality and undergraduate library usage. Data were collected using an adapted

questionnaire as the research instrument. The target population consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in private universities in Ogun State.

A random sampling technique was utilized to distribute the questionnaire among the study population. The sample size of 370 students was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan table, with 158 students from Babcock University, 130 from Bells University of Technology, 45 from Crescent University, and 37 from Macpherson University.

Out of the distributed questionnaires, 255 were returned and included in the analysis. Data analysis was conducted using percentages and mean scores to assess the perceptions and experiences of undergraduate students regarding library service quality and usage patterns.

Table 1: Sample size

S/n	Name of Institutions	Administered Questionnaire	Returned
1	Babcock University	158	115
2	Bells University of Technology	130	87
3	Crescent University	45	32
4	Macpherson	37	21
	Total	370	255

Result and Discussion Of Findings

RQ 1: What is the level of library service quality provided by libraries to undergraduates in private Universities in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Level of library service quality rendered by libraries to undergraduates in private Universities in Ogun State, Nigeria

Items	To a very high level	Moderately high level	Low level	To a very low level	Mean
Affect of Service					
I can access the library's electronic resources from my home or hostel	38(14.0%)	95(38.3%)	65(25.5%)	57(22.1%)	2.44
The library has a website that enables me to locate information on my own	44(16.6%)	116(47.2%)	56(21.7%)	39(14.5%)	2.66
The library's opening and closing hours are convenient	66(26.0%)	147(60.4%)	31(11.1%)	11(2.6%)	3.10

The library helps me stay abreast of developments in my field (s) of interest	70(27.7%)	135(55.3%)	41(15.3%)	9(1.7%)	3.09
The library aids my advancement in my academic discipline or work	73(28.9%)	140(57.4%)	35(12.8%)	7(.9%)	3.14
The library helps me distinguish between accurate and inaccurate information.	68(26.8%)	123(50.2%)	55(21.3%)	9(1.7%)	3.02
The library provides me with the information skills i need in my work or study.	52(20.0%)	155(63.8%)	41(15.3%)	7(.9%)	3.03
It is easy to make a compliment, complaint or suggestion about any condition about the library	52(20.0%)	131(53.6%)	57(22.1)	15(4.3%)	2.89
I can access the library’s electronic resources from my home or hostel	39(14.5%)	91(36.6%)	77(30.6%)	48(18.3%)	2.47
					Weighted Mean
					2.87
Library as a place					
The library has physical facilities that are visually appealing	63 (24.7%)	162 (66.8%)	23 (7.7%)	7 (.8%)	3.15
The library has a convenient operating hours to users	67 (26.4%)	154 (63.4%)	25 (8.5%)	9 (1.7%)	3.14
There is proper arrangement of print resources in the library	56 (21.7%)	157 (64.7%)	31 (11.1%)	11 (2.6%)	3.06
I can access library resources remotely from my hostel or my home. there is library website where i can lodge complain and navigate for information in library database.	34(12.3%)	85(34.0%)	93(37.4%)	43(16.2%)	2.43
The library is in a comfortable and inviting location	57(22.1%)	160 (66.0%)	31(11.1%)	7(.9%)	3.09
The library space is attractive, conducive and inspires study and learning	69 (27.2%)	143 (58.7%)	35 (12.8%)	8(1.3%)	3.12
Directional signs, brochures and statements associated with services are available to guide users	61(23.0%)	164(67.2%)	30(9.8%)		3.13
The library as a learning hub provides a community space for group learning and study	52(20.0%)	158(65.1%)	34(12.3%)	11(2.6%)	3.03
Lighting and ventilation are conducive for reading	76(29.4%)	149(60.9%)	30(9.8%)		3.20
					Weighted Mean
					2.7
					Grand Mean
					2.8

Decision rule: If Mean is ≥ 0 to 1=very low level, 1.1 to 2=Low level, 2.1 to 3=moderately high level, 3.1 to 4=Very high level

The table 1 shows the responses about quality of library services. The Grand mean is 2.8

which indicated that the level of quality of services rendered by the libraries to undergraduate students is moderately high. This corroborated a survey result of Coleman, Xian, Bair and Chollatt (1997) that showed a discrepancy in the quality of the services

provided by the library and those desired by its customers.

RQ 2: What is the extent of use of library by undergraduates in private Universities, Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Extent of use of library Resources by undergraduates in private Universities, Ogun State, Nigeria

Items	To A Very High Extent	Moderately high Extent	Low Extent	To A Very Low Extent	Mean
Library Resources					
Journals	65(25.5%)	129(52.8%)	35(12.8%)	24(8.1%)	2.97
Textbooks	93(37.4%)	133(54.5%)	19(6.0%)	10(2.1%)	3.27
Newspapers	33(11.9%)	142(58.3%)	48(18.3%)	32(11.5%)	2.71
E-resources	73(28.9%)	125(51.1%)	40(14.9%)	17(5.1%)	3.04
OPAC: Online Public Access Catalogue	56(21.7%)	130(53.2%)	56(21.7%)	13(3.4%)	2.93
Past Projects	61(23.8%)	154(63.4%)	31(11.1%)	9(1.7%)	3.09
					Weighed Mean 3.00

Decision rule: If Mean is ≥ 0 to 1=very low extent, 1.1 to 2=Low extent, 2.1 to 3=moderately high extent, 3.1 to 4=Very high extent

The responses to the second research question revealed a moderately high extent of library usage with overall grand mean of 3.0. This result is similar to the study of Fagyan et al. (2023) in which students expressed moderate satisfaction when it had to do with library resources. When students are satisfied with library resources, it translates to major implications in their education as well as library services (Johnson et al., 2023). Positive comments mean that libraries are satisfying students' academic needs and providing both useful and accessible materials. Library resource relevance affects satisfaction. Undergraduate students of this generation require a wide range of tools to study various

emerging yet challenging courses (Williams, 2021). And these libraries are saddled with the responsibility to satisfy patrons, support students' academic interests and encourage lifelong learning. Smith, (2020) negated the finding of this study. It asserted that statistical analysis at Covenant University, found that students use the online public access catalogue more frequently than the manual catalogue. George (2022) asserted that the issue with catalog use is connected to respondents' lack of information about how to use the library catalog therefore there is the need for assistance by librarians to put users through the use of OPAC.

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of library service quality on library usage by undergraduate students in private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Significant influence of library service quality on libraries usage by undergraduate students in private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.644a	.415	.412	.26799

a. Predictors: (Constant), service quality

ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.855	1	11.855	165.061	.000b
	Residual	16.734	233	.072		
	Total	28.589	234			

A. Dependent variable: usage of library

B. Predictors: (constant), service quality

Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.207	.141		8.541	.000
	service quality	.610	.047	.644	12.848	.000

a. Dependent Variable: usage of library

The Table 3 above indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting "usage of library" based on the predictor "service quality." the positive coefficient for "service quality" suggests that improvements in service quality are associated with an increase in library usage. The moderate correlation (R) and reasonable R squared value indicate that a substantial portion of the variance in library usage can be attributed to service quality. The adjusted R squared value suggests that this relationship remains significant even after adjusting for the number of predictors in the model. On the strength of this result (Adj. R² = 0.412, F(1,233) = 165.061, p = 0.000), this study therefore rejects the null hypothesis

(H₀₁) which state that service quality will not have significant influence on usage of library among undergraduates of private universities in Ogun State. Overall, based on the provided data, it appears that service quality plays a significant role in influencing library usage.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from this study that quality of service rendered by the libraries to undergraduate in private universities significantly influence library usage positively.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. There is need for training and retraining with respect to the quality of services rendered by the librarian to the students. All aspect of service (affect, information control and library as a building) must be put into serious consideration
2. Library management should come up with constant users' perspective evaluation strategies encompassing all aspect of library services.

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